

APPLICATION OF X-RAY COMPUTED MICRO-TOMOGRAPHY TO THE STUDY OF DAMAGE AND OXIDATION KINETICS OF THERMOSTRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Thermostructural composites are three dimensional (3D) structured materials. Weakening phenomena (mechanical and chemical) are hardly 3D and take place inside the material. X-Ray Computed Micro-Tomography (μ CT) is then a recent solution which allows experimental studies of these phenomenons. The technique is applied to the study of failure for mechanical loading and to the oxidation of self healing phases. Results are useful data to verify or invalidate hypotheses or estimations realised in modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermostructural composites are generally composed of a woven ceramic or carbon fibre reinforcement and a ceramic and/or carbon matrix. This class of material exhibits interesting thermo-mechanical properties, especially at very high temperatures. Indeed, the intrinsic brittleness of the components is counteracted by crack deviation mechanisms, leading to a material fragilization and a controlled progressive damage; the excellent stiffness of the refractory constituents is thus fully utilized [1]. This material is therefore used in strategic and high-tech domains where their thermo-mechanical behaviour must be perfectly controlled. The fragile behaviour of phases can cause micro-cracks that are paths for the penetration of corrosive gases; internal protection is provided by the presence of self-healing phases. In the multilayer matrix, there is a B_4C layer, which turns itself into B_2O_3 glass upon oxidation, capable of blocking the progression of oxygen. But the crack forming and self-healing processes are difficult to analyse and control. μ CT gives the possibility of in-situ 3D imaging and analysis of the material at different resolutions while mechanically loading it, giving access to a very precise insight of damage.

Several studies are available on the progressive failure of the components in SiC/SiC thermostructural composites ([2], [3]...). Former studies have been carried out on minicomposites (i.e. small unidirectional composite samples) representative of a yarn of the actual composite. These studies were first conducted post mortem using chemical etching to reveal cracks (they are closed when the load is slacked off) or using in-situ SEM tensile tests [4]. The drawback of tests under SEM is the inability to observe the damage kinetics inside the sample. More recently, Chateau *et al.* [3] performed in-situ tensile tests at ESRF on SiC/SiC minicomposites produced at CEA Saclay and have successfully managed to fully characterize the progressive damage, featuring crack production kinetics and a non-linear tensile behaviour law. Bale *et al.* [5] published the last results on in-situ CT tensile tests at high temperature on SiC/SiC composites and minicomposites.

In this project, the aim is to extend this methodology to self-healing ceramic-matrix composites. Work has been done in two directions: first, tensile tests have been performed on unidirectional minicomposites (plain SiC_f/SiC and SiC_f/layered self-healing matrix), while taking high-resolution tomographs (0.7 μ m/voxel). Second, the oxidation front in composites samples with 3D woven reinforcements has been tracked by μ CT at a lesser resolution (1 μ m/voxel). However, simultaneous investigation of damage and self-healing glass formation requires ex-situ analyses, in which the sample is oxidized outside the μ CT device and inserted again for tomographic imaging. The produced

3D images are then processed to study the damage or oxidation kinetics. The goal of this second study is to observe the oxidation front inside the material and thus to verify a kinetic oxidation model ([6], [7]). Some results presented in this paper are available in Caty et al. [8] and recent advances are also presented.

2. DAMAGE INVESTIGATIONS

The first study has been carried out on two types of samples. First, previously prepared SiC_f/SiC minicomposites [9] processed by CVI and taped. This tape was realised using a tungsten wire wound around the minicomposite to obtain relative volume amounts of phases close to the one measured in the yarn of the final composite (34% fibre, 53% matrix and 13 % pores). A radiograph of the entire sample is proposed on figure 1-c. Its dimensions are 7 mm length and 0.48 mm average diameter. Self-healing small size composites have also been investigated but all tests have failed because of sliding in grips and will not be presented.

In-situ tensile tests were realised at ESRF ID19 line on INSA Lyon's specific tensile device [10] (see Figure 1-a). The tensile test, displacement driven, was regularly interrupted to perform tomographic scans of the entire minicomposite (5 images along the height at $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ resolution). In the meanwhile, a continuous radiographic acquisition was done to follow the damage kinetics in the central part of the composite.

Figure 1: Experimental process used to study damage in ceramic-matrix minicomposites. (a) Micro-tensile device [10] (b) Strain/load curve of the in-situ tensile test. (c) Radiographs of the material for the different strain states labelled in Figure 1-b. Some initial cracks are circled in red.

The image processing method was inspired by Chateau *et al.* [3] works. It consists in revealing cracks by following the evolution of the grey scale levels in the loading direction (here, vertical). In the present work, the method has been improved by the use of a derivative (Sobel or “edge-detection”) filter to reveal cracks. Crack counting is then carried out by peak detection applied to vertical profiles of the image. We found it sufficient to work directly on radiographs instead of the fully reconstructed

tomographs. Figure 1-c shows a radiograph series for different loadings (the corresponding load/strain is indicated on figure 1-b): cracks are not easy to distinguish by eye, which justifies the use of Sobel filtering to reveal them. It is then possible to calculate the position, number and time step of each crack for different loading states. These data are useful for modelling the damage elastic behaviour of these materials.

Second, the spreading of each crack inside the material has been investigated in more detail. Cracks are this time analysed in the tomographic reconstruction and their spreading is studied as a function of the load. The first step is to bring out the crack using a Sobel filter. Then the crack is visualised and a map of its vertical position is built for each loading step. The results are presented on figure 2. Many cracks propagate helicoidally, starting from the sample edge, and do not traverse the sample central part. This result is consistent with the observations realised by Chateau *et al.* [3]. On the other hand, it is in disagreement with the usual 1D hypothesis used to model the behaviour of the minicomposites, which assumes a sudden spreading in the section perpendicular to the loading direction ([11], [12] for exemple).

Figure 2 : Study of the crack spreading inside the minicomposite. (a) 3D visualisation of a central zone of the sample at 130N loading. (b) Altitude map of the crack position for different loadings, the value of which is indicated on the upper left corner (30N, 60N, 80N, 100N and 117N).

3. OXIDATION INVESTIGATIONS

The second study has been carried out on small specimens ($1.7 \times 1.7 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$) of woven composites processed by Herakles (SAFRAN Group). Regarding the oxidation durations of several tens of hours, this study is difficult to be run in-situ on synchrotron beamlines. The solution was then to carry out ex-situ tests and scan the material on a laboratory tomograph (Tomomat Bordeaux : GE - Phoenix XRay - Nanotom, and on a XRadia - VersaXRM500). Oxidation was carried out at LCTS in a Pyrox oven at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with local air. One initial state and two states after 15h and 30h were examined by μCT . Images are then analysed comparing the same zone on the different states. The objective is to detect a B_4C consumption corresponding to the apparition of density changes inside the multi-sequenced matrix.

On figure 3 the oxidation progression is followed across two zones close to the edge of the composite sample, using four tomographic slices made on the XRadia-Versa XRM500 with $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ of resolution (in local tomography mode). Fig. 5a compares the initial state and the state after 80 h of oxidation in the same conditions as before, while Fig. 5b shows another zone after 40 h and 80 h of treatment. Due to the difficulty to accurately zoom on a precise zone in local tomography mode, we have not been

able to focus on a single zone at all times, but on two distinct zones. The main result of this characterisation is to highlight the lack of homogeneity of oxidation progression fronts in the volume, as compared to observations on cross sections from previous studies. At 40 h of oxidation, the front depth varies from 80 μm inside the yarn to 130 μm in pure boron carbide areas. After 80 h, the consumed depth ranges between 100 μm and 250 μm . The consumed thicknesses for a monolithic material in this condition, as calculated by the 1D model, are respectively 85 μm at 40 h and 170 μm at 80 h in a rather good agreement with the average experimental values.

Figure 3 : Study of the oxidation kinetics (a) two oxidation states : initial and after 80h and (b) after 40h and 80h. Focus on two zones on the border of the composite sample, where oxidation appears.

Figure 4 present a 3D rendering of the oxydation front inside the sample. This picture illustrate the influence of macropores and arrangements of the phases on the oxidation progresses inside the material.

This motivates the development of enhanced models of oxidation progression in a complex architecture. Several directions are possible, for instance projection of the 3D system in a 1D model [13], or the production of 2D models placed in crack planes, currently under development [14]. These models are intended to incorporate in the long term all the morphological elements that can be extracted from tomographic scans.

Figure 4 : Study of the oxydation front position in the sample at 40h. (a) slice, (b) the slice and a part of the 3 D front with a 3D rendering visualisation and (c) the whole 3D front.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Progressive damage of minicomposites has been studied on minicomposites. Using radiographs, local crack development kinetics inside the material were investigated. By μCT , a progression in helix shape was found, as shown by Chateau et al. [3]. This observation invalidates the usual 1D hypothesis present in classical CMC damage models. Further work is to obtain the same data on SiC_f /multilayer

self-healing minicomposites.

A tomographic study of ceramic-matrix composites with self-healing matrix allowed checking the consistency between measurements and existing oxidation models of monolithic materials. It has been found that this agreement is limited to early moments of oxidation, due to the increasing effects of the 3D arrangement of diffusion pathways (mostly open pores) and phases. The tests highlight the interest of a global 3D analysis and modelling of the oxidation process.

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